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7. T. A. GRISMAN, "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds", Pergamon Press, New York, 1962, p. 423.
8. Ref. 7, p. 122.
9. Ref. 7, p. 337.

and Kashmir State. The local inhabitants in this high altitude desert consume the seeds of this plant as a dietary item. General composition of this legume has already been reported¹. The present communication deals with the fatty acid constituents of the seeds oil.

Fatty Acid Composition of *Cicer soongaricum* Steph. Seed Oil

S. K. KATIYAR* and A. K. BHATIA

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu Tawi-180 001

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Experimental

The seeds of *C. soongaricum* were collected during ethnobiological survey from South Pullu area (near Khardung La Pass, altitude 5 000 m MSL). The healthy and mature seeds were dried and ground upto 100-120 mesh.

The oil was solvent extracted using petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and purified by the method of Folch *et al.*². Methyl esters of the fatty acids were obtained by saponification of the oil, removal of

CICER soongaricum Steph. (fam.: Leguminosae; local name *Sarri*) grows wild at an altitude of 3,000-5,000-m MSL in the Ladakh area of Jammu

Fig. 1. G10 separation of fatty acids of *C. soongaricum* seed oil, I, II = unidentified peak.

unsaponifiable matter and esterification of the sample with 4% hydrochloric acid in methanol at 70-90° for 12-14 h³. Different fatty acids in the form of methyl esters were analysed through glc. The operating conditions of glc were: Pye-Unticam 204 instrument, Reoplex glass column (6 mm × 2 m), F.I.D. detector, nitrogen flow rate 35 ml min⁻¹, column temperature 180, isothermal condition, injection port temperature 270, detector 300. Peak area was calculated by triangulation method. Physical characteristics of the seed oil were studied by the reported method⁴.

The seeds contain 7.2% oil. Physical characteristics of the oil were: refractive index 1.472, iodine value 107, saponification value 193. The unsaponifiable matter found to be 4.5% is quite high in comparison to other reported Indian gram varieties⁵.

Results and Discussion

Among the various fatty acids, linoleic acid predominated (37.13%). Stearic, lauric and linolenic acids were found to be 25.38, 23.05 and 6.10%, respectively, while myristic, palmitic and arachidic acids were in lesser concentrations. The glc graph (Fig. 1) showed two unidentified peaks, one after lauric acid (peak-I) and other after palmitic acid (peak-II) whose concentrations were 3.4 and 2.18%, respectively. It is significant to note that *C. soongaricum* seeds oil is a rich source of essential fatty acids, viz. linoleic and linolenic acids (43.23%). In addition of fulfilling dietary requirements, the essential fatty acids are also precursors in the biosynthesis of prostaglandins which in trace amounts are necessary for various physiological activities.

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References

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Chemical Investigation of *Holoptelea integrifolia* Planch. and *Cassia fistula* Linn.

K. M. BISWAS* and HAIMANTI MALLIK

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta,
92 A P.C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

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HOLOPTELEA *integrifolia* Planch. (Ulmaceae) is the only species of the genus *Holoptelea* occurring in India. Several triterpenoids¹⁻³, aliphatic

alcohols¹ and acids⁴ were isolated from this plant. *Cassia fistula* Linn. (Leguminosae) is one of the commonest trees of India. All its parts were previously investigated and several anthraquinones⁵⁻¹⁰, flavonoids^{6,7,9}, and aliphatic alcohols^{5,11}, acids¹¹ and esters¹¹ were isolated. Both these plants have medicinal uses^{12,13}. Reinvestigation of the stem bark of *H. integrifolia* has resulted in the isolation of 2-aminonaphthaquinone (yield, 0.0013%), friedelin (0.002%), epifriedelinol (0.0053%), β -sitosterol (0.004%) and its β -D-glucoside (0.01%), while that of the flowers of *C. fistula* yielded aurantiamide acetate (0.011%), β -sitosterol (0.006%), its β -D-glucoside (0.02%) and an uncharacterised fatty acid ester of β -sitosterol (CF-1) (0.001%). Although 2-aminonaphthaquinone is synthetically known¹⁴, to our knowledge, there is no previous report of its natural occurrence.

Holoptelea integrifolia Planch. :

Air dried and powdered stem bark of *H. integrifolia* (1.5 kg), collected from Midnapore district in West Bengal during October was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus for 40 h each first with petroleum ether and then with chloroform. The petroleum ether extract on concentration and cooling deposited a yellowish white solid which was collected by filtration. Chromatography of the solid on a silica gel column gave friedelin (eluate: petroleum ether-benzene, 1:1) and epifriedelinol (benzene), and that of the concentrate of the filtrate furnished the same two compounds and β -sitosterol (benzene-chloroform, 1:1). The concentrate of the chloroform extract on similar chromatography afforded 2-aminonaphthaquinone (chloroform-methanol, 49:1) and β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside (chloroform-methanol, 9:1).

2-Aminonaphthaquinone crystallised in orange-red needles, m.p. 205° (lit.¹⁴ 205°) from chloroform-petroleum ether; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) (log ϵ) 233 (3.98), 266 (4.19), 333 (3.20) and 445 nm (3.44); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3370-3180 (NH), 1685 (C=O), 1625, 1570, 1420, 1365, 1270, 1220, 1125, 980, 825 and 720 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 5.16 (2H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, 2-NH₂), 5.97 (1H, s, H-3), 7.55-7.78 (2H, m, H-6 and H-7) and 7.97-8.11 (2H, m, H-5 and H-8); *m/e* (rel. int.) 173 (100, M⁺), 146 (93, M-HCN), 145 (49, M-CO), 118 (43, M-HCN-CO), 117 (93, M-2CO), 105 (96, M-HCN-CHCO), 104 (91, M-HCN-CH₂CO), 77 (88) and 76 (79). On treatment with ethanolic 0.5 N HCl, 2-aminonaphthaquinone furnished 2-hydroxynaphthaquinone, crystallising from chloroform-petroleum ether as yellow needles, m.p. 150° d (lit.¹⁵ 192° d). The formation of 2-hydroxynaphthaquinone by acid hydrolysis of 2-aminonaphthaquinone indicates that the latter behaves as a vinylogous amide, not as an amine. The insolubility of 2-aminonaphthaquinone in dilute acids and its resistance to acetylation at room temperature with acetic anhydride and pyridine also support this view.

The other isolates were identified by direct comparison with their authentic samples as well as their spectral data (ir, uv, nmr, etc.).